

Things You Should Know About Diamond-like Carbon Coatings

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Abstract

During the last decades there has been an increased interest in the use of Diamond-Like Carbon (DLC) coatings in many industrial applications like automotive, and aerospace. These coatings can be tailored in order to provide high toughness, high elasticity, low wear, and very low friction coefficient. In this work, we will discuss the nature of these coatings, and we will show how they can be designed in order to be used in steel bearings and gears for wind applications.

1. Introduction

Sol Aisenberg and Ronald Chabot discussed in 1971 the properties of a carbon-based coating deposited from a plasma source using an energetic carbon ion-beam. Their films resulted to be a very hard amorphous material that resembled the mechanical properties of diamond rather than graphite. They tagged the coatings as “diamond-like carbon” (DLC), and the research on carbon-based coatings for tribological applications took-off [1]. During the 1970s and 1980s some researchers started to get interested in these kinds of film, while in the 1990’s the research got momentum, as can be seen in Figure 1. The numbers of scientific publication and patent have been increasing every year, while numerous applications are being offered in the automotive and aerospace commercial market.

In the following sections we will review the nature of these coatings and how they can be obtained by different deposition methods. We will then show how they can be designed in order to be used in steel bearings and gears for wind applications.

2. Bonding Configurations in Carbon-based Coatings

Besides the well-known diamond and graphite single-crystals, carbon exhibits other allotropic forms such as fullerene molecules, nanotubes, nanowires, two-dimensional graphene crystals, nano-crystalline graphite, semi-crystalline carbon black, and amorphous glassy carbon [2] [3]. The number of forms is a consequence of carbon being the only element in the periodic table having isomers with 0, 1, 2, or 3 dimensions. The four valence electrons of carbon are able to form three major bond configurations, as shown in Figure 2: the sp^3 tetrahedral bonds like in diamond, the sp^2 planar bonds like in graphite, and the sp bonds like in alkynes. The elongated atomic orbitals indicated in the figure are the hybrids that form s-type molecular orbitals, while the roundish atomic orbitals are remaining 2p electron(s) that form the π -type molecular orbitals [1].

The sp^3 and sp^2 bonds can occur not only in single crystals, like diamond and graphite respectively, but also in amorphous solids where the atoms are in a random network, with bonding only between a few individual atoms. Amorphous carbon films containing a mixture of sp^2 and sp^3 bonds are known under the generic name of diamond-like coatings (DLC) because they display some of the typical properties of diamonds.

The bonding configuration in a C-based coating will mainly depend on the selected deposition method. Figure 3 shows a ternary phase diagram for various amorphous carbon-based coatings according to their sp^2 , sp^3 , and H content. The structure phase diagram consists of three regions [1] [3]:

- ***H-free C coatings along the left axis.*** The H-free sp^2 amorphous carbon (a-C) is typically a coating deposited by pyrolysis of hydrocarbon polymers or by evaporation. Amorphous coatings with a mixture of sp^2 and sp^3 bonds, but not containing H, are DLC coatings typically deposited by sputtering and laser deposition in ultra-high vacuum (UHV) conditions. When the amount of sp^3 is high, McKenzie has suggested denoting the material as tetrahedral amorphous carbon (ta-C) in order to distinguish it from sp^2 a-C [2]. Tetrahedral bonding at levels of approximately 80% can be found in amorphous carbon films deposited by cathodic arc deposition, ion beam deposition, and laser ablation.
- ***Very-high H content region.*** The H content is so high that the material cannot be deposited in a solid phase. The regions are delimited by C_2H_2 in the composition on the bottom axis and $(CH_2)_n$ on the right axis of the triangle.
- ***Hydrogenated C coatings.*** The third region, between by the other ones, features both amorphous hydrogenated carbon films (a-C:H) and tetrahedral hydrogenated amorphous carbon (ta-C:H). The a-C:H is typically produced by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) techniques using hydrocarbon precursors or by reactive magnetron sputtering of carbon

targets in mixtures of Ar and H atmospheres. ta-C:H can be deposited by high density plasmas such as electron cyclotron resonance (ECR) deposition.

Two keys parameters in determining the physical properties of carbon coatings are the sp^3/sp^2 fraction and the H content. For non-hydrogenated films, the mechanical properties (hardness and Young's modulus) essentially scale with the fraction of sp^3 carbon in the film. That is since the sp^3 bonds allow for a higher packing density, and the three dimensional bonding gives a higher strength of the material. The hydrogenated films also can have a high fraction of sp^3 bonds, but since the three-dimensional structure may frequently become terminated by hydrogen, the mechanical strength, as well as the density decreases with increasing H-content [1] .

An important advantage of DLC coatings is that they can be deposited at low temperatures (< 180 °C). This makes DLC an ideal low-friction wear-resistant coating on heat-sensitive substrates, such as hardened bearing steels. DLC is classically obtained by Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD) processing in low or medium vacuum environments [1].

New advances using pulsed plasmas have made possible to obtain films of unprecedented adhesion to the steel substrates [1] [4]. Recently, the use of high power impulse magnetron sputtering (HIPIMS) technology has been proposed to increase the adhesion of coatings on metal substrates. HIPIMS produces a high flux of ions with high metal content similar to an arc discharge, but without droplets. The ions (gas and metals) are accelerated to the substrate by the use of a DC bias, producing a high rate of substrate etching and also the implantation of metal atoms like in arc discharges. Based in an innovation, it has been reported the deposition of highly adherent carbon-based films on SKF3 steel substrates using a novel HIPIMS pretreatment in an industrial production chamber [5]. During the pretreatment, the substrates were pulse-biased in the environment of a HIPIMS Cr plasma in order to sputter clean the surface and to implant Cr+ metal ions, as shown in Figure 4a (left panel). Subsequently, carbon-based films with superior adhesion to the steel substrates were obtained by DC unbalanced magnetron sputtering.

The microstructure of the interface between the carbon-based coating and SKF3 steel substrates was studied by cross-sectional TEM in samples deposited with the HIPIMS biased substrate method (Figure 4a). Figure 4b shows the formation of a modified Cr layer between the steel substrate and a carbon-based film prepared by this method. The layer is characterized by a polycrystalline structure of approximately 100 nm. The transition between the substrate and the modified layer, consisting of a ~5 nm amorphous layer, is visible between the Cr and the steel. The overall structure of the interface is dense, with no formation of bubbles or voids, pointing to a strong bonding between the steel substrate and the carbon-based coating [4].

3. Advanced Nanostructured DLC

One of the problems of DLC coatings is the presence of high compressive stresses in the film. These stresses create a technological problem when depositing films exceeding a micron-thick, which is necessary in many tribological applications. Stress management techniques have been suggested, like thermal stress annealing, and DLC-doping with metals. Unfortunately, thermal annealing is not possible in some steel alloys, where the maximum allowed temperature is about 180 °C. The doping of metals, such as Ti, W, Ta, Cr, and Si, decreases effectively the compressive stresses, but also typically leads to a reduction of hardness, since carbide bond forming competes with sp^3 bond forming required for a highest hardness. Another more recent approach is the deposition of multilayer coating architectures, where DLC layers are separated with metal layers and incorporated in a functionally gradient coating to accommodate stresses [6].

An example of the multilayer coating is the advanced DLC multilayered coating “NoWear®” patented by SKF, which contains a metal in the diamond-like amorphous-hydrogenated-carbon

matrix that have shown an improved tribological behavior [7]. Figure 5 shows a cross-sectional scanning electron microscopy view of the engineered NoWear® coating. We can observe the presence adhesion layer designed by SKF (A); multilayers of WC/C lamellas (B) and the presence on the top of a run-in graphitic layer (C) [7].

4. Applications

NoWear® is a wear-resistant carbon coating that can be applied to the rolling elements and inner ring raceway(s) of a bearing, or only the rolling elements as shown in Figure 6. A PVD process applies the wear-resistant carbon coating with thickness ranging from 2 to 4 μm , depending on the size of the bearing. The hardness of the coating is 1200 Hv_{10} , which contrast with the hardened bearing steel hardness $\text{Hv}_{10} = 800$. NoWear® coated bearing surfaces retain the toughness of the underlying material while adopting the hardness, improved friction properties and wear-resistance of the coating.

During the running-in period, minute amounts of the coating material are transferred to the counter-surfaces. This coating reduces friction and improves resistance against wear and smearing, even in bearings where only the rolling elements are coated. Engineered NoWear® coated bearings from SKF can eliminate or reduce wear when having long periods of insufficient lubrication, sudden variations in load, rapid speed changes, vibrations and oscillations, like in energy-wind applications [7] [8].

Features

- High Wear-resistance
Coating hardness: $H_V = 1200$
Steel hardness: $H_V = 800$
- Very tolerant to contamination
- Tolerant to poor lubrication
- High-speed capabilities through unique coating properties

Figure 6: Example of a NoWear® SKF coated bearing

Tests have shown that NoWear® coating has 4 times lower friction coefficient in dry conditions, and about 15-30% lower friction in boundary lubrication. NoWear® bearings can withstand longer periods of insufficient lubrication, sudden variations in load, rapid speed changes, vibrations and oscillation.

Figure 7: Smearing test with suddenly applied load, bearing type 22222 E/C3, NoWear® vs a bare steel roller.

Smearing test with suddenly applied load for a spherical roller bearing 22222 E/C3 have shown that NoWear® coated rollers overpass the behavior of non-coated steel rollers. Figure 7 compares the speed-dimension factor nd_m for a coated and for a non-coated roller. The speed-dimension factor is calculated as $nd_m = n(D+d)/2$, where D and d are the outer diameter of the

outer ring and the bore diameter of the inner ring, respectively; n is the rotation speed of the bearing, i.e., the number of revolutions per minute. In the case of a bare steel roller, smearing damage takes place at about 250000 mm/min, while that for a NoWear® coated roller the measurement was suspended with a $nd_m = 800000$ mm/min, having the rolling element and raceways no signs of smearing or any other kind of damage.

The engineered NoWear® coatings is already used in many different applications. In the area of wind energy, it has successfully been used in 2 and 3 MW windmills (Figure 8).

Successful Application
2 and 3 MW windmill
turbine gear units with
SKF NoWear®
cylindrical roller bearings

- *Improved Service Life*
- *Avoid damage at low load*

Figure 8: Applications in the wind turbine area

5. Final Remarks

Carbon-based coatings enjoy a growing interest in industrial applications. By tuning the C sp³-to-sp² bonding ratio, by doping and alloying the carbon with other elements, and by the deposition of multilayer coating architectures, researchers have been able to tailor unique physical, mechanical, and tribological properties in order to satisfy increasing technological demands. This paper has focused on explaining the different kind of DLC coatings in order to bring some light on different terminology, technical aspects, and coating design. In particular we have discussed the engineered NoWear® coating, and have shown how these coatings on lubricated rubbing and rolling contacts can help to improve a new generation of wind turbines.

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